

United Nations Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria: An Appraisal of Oritamefa Baptist Model Schools, Ibadan

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Abstract: *Development is a process that brings around something in the form of growth and progress. At the centre of every conceptualisation of development is the idea of change. What development stands for is a dynamic change that gives room for new access to man for the better living condition with a high degree reduction in the cost of production. It is on this background that this paper focuses on the assessment of the rapid progress that OritaMefa Baptist Model Schools, Ibadan experienced in recent times. The paper investigates the reasons why the schools have been performing excellently in their final year West African Examination Council (WAEC) and Nigeria Examination Council (NECO) and also their contributions to the attainment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs) in Nigeria. The paper in its methodology makes use of historical and case study designs and oral and secondary data collections to enrich its findings. The papers' findings are that Orita-Mefa Baptist Model Schools have contributed immensely to the development of the education sector and in the reduction of poverty and joblessness in no small measure in Nigeria. The paper among others, therefore, recommends that the schools should extend their tentacles to other parts of Nigeria communities to enable other people of other states to enjoy the benefit of their educational advancement. Finally, the paper concludes that the schools' management should possibly consider scholarship and other forms of assistance to the children of the less-privileged people in the society not minding their academic achievements.*

Keywords: *Oritamefa, Baptist, United- Nations, Sustainable Development Goals, Nigeria, Educational.*

I. Introduction

Baptist is a term that is generally used to describe individuals that belong to a Baptist church or a Baptist denomination. The name "Baptist" is derived from a conviction that followers of Jesus Christ are commanded to be baptised (by immersion in water) as a public display of their faith.¹ Furthermore, Baptist Christians are commonly identified as Christians who emphasize the authority of the Scriptures; salvation through faith in Christ; believers' baptism by immersion; congregational church government; and religious liberty.²

OritaMefa Baptist church came into existence as a result of the aspiration to meet the spiritual needs of non-Yoruba speaking people living in Ibadan during the years 1946-1956. Some of these people were Europeans, Americans, Asians, people from the Middle East and other African countries. These were attracted to the industry institutions of higher learning and the high life of the urban population which the city of Ibadan offered.³ The Women Missionary Union (WMU) were the first to act by starting a Sunday school at the old premises of the Baptist mission headquarters, Agodi Gate before the church later moved to the present venue at Total Garden. The church was first known as Baptist Chapel Ibadan and the first worship took place on December 15, 1957, with Dr I.N. Patterson, then General Secretary of the Nigerian Baptist Convention who

preached the first message.⁴ Furthermore, the Baptist chapel was organised into a church formally on May 21, 1967, with the new name, OritaMefa Baptist Church, Ibadan.⁵

Historically, after many prayerful and thoughtful considerations and foresight, the primary arm of the church academic institutions was founded by members of OBC under the leadership of Revd C.M. Bowers who was the American Pastor of the church at the time. The Nursery and Primary School opened its doors to the first batch of children on the 19th of January, 1970 with Mrs F.A. Adeniyi as its first and foundation headmistress.

The secondary arm was founded in 1996 to provide quality education and a conducive spiritual and moral environment for pupils and children of the church and from other schools, through the vision God gave the Pastor by then, Rev. S.M. Leigh. This enabled many pupils of the Nursery and Primary (OBS) to gain admission into the Model school to continue their education within the Baptist setting. The aims and objectives are to reduce the high numbers of the students who are roaming about the street because of incessant teachers strikes; to allow those who finished at the primary level to gain admission and to avoid travelling very far to Federal Government Colleges to gain admission which had caused premature death through accidents as a result of bad roads and reckless driving. In order words, “the church felt the need to provide quality education for children who will be leaders tomorrow. In addition, the church opined that the school would also provide employment opportunities for the jobless youths and thereby assist the government in providing jobs for the citizens”. The pioneer Principal was Mrs Bolanle Olabisi and the first intakes were 115 students. As of the end of the 2007/2008 academic session, the numerical strength of the school had risen from the modest 115 students to over 1000 students. The current student population (as at the 2019/2020 session) was 1820, the outlets in Ring Road that was founded in 2002 has a total number of 720 students and the newly founded Akobo Annex that came on board in January 2020 has a total of about 250 students.

Based on these premises, this paper considers the roles and contributions of OritaMefa Baptist Model Schools to the attainment of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria. The findings of this paper are that the schools have distinguished themselves in their contributions to the development of the education sector, job provisions, and elimination of poverty in Nigeria. The paper is also of the opinion that the schools need to extend their hands of generosity to the children of low estate and to establish more branches of the school to other parts of Nigeria. The paper finally concludes that the schools' Management Boards should take steps that will help them retain their leadership position in their external examination performances in Nigeria.

II. Historical Background and Development of Sustainable Development Goals

The concept of United Nations Sustainable Development is often said to have originated from the 1987 Brundtland Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development titled “Our Common Future”. The report gives a definition of sustainable development which gained global acceptance among sustainability practitioners, researchers and activists among others. According to the Brundtland Report, sustainable development refers to “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”⁸

In addition, the sustainable development goals are a collection of 17 global goals designed to be “blueprints to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all.”⁹ The SDGs were set in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly and intended to be achieved by the year 2030 Agenda.¹⁰ The goals are broad-based and interdependent. Each of the 17 sustainable goals has a list of targets that are measured with indicators. To make the SDGs successful, data on the 17 goals have been made available in an easily understood form. A variety of tools exist to track and visualize progress towards the goals.¹¹ Historically, in 1972, governments met in Stockholm, Sweden for the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment to consider the rights of the family to a healthy and productive environment.¹² In 1983, the UN created the world commission on Environment (later known as the Brundtland Commission), which defined sustainable development as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future to meet their needs.”¹³

Furthermore, in January 2013, the 30-member UN General Assembly Open Working Group on Sustainable Development Goals was established to identify specific goals for the SDGs. The Open Working

Group (OWG) was tasked with preparing a proposal on the SDGs for presentation during the 68th General Session September 2013 – September 2014.¹⁴ Likewise, on 5th December, 2014 the UN General Assembly accepted the Secretary General’s Synthesis Report, which stated that the agenda for the post-2015 SDG process will be based on the OWG proposals.¹⁵ Finally, on the 25th of September, 2015 the 193 countries of the UN General Assembly adopted the 2030 Development Agenda titled “Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.”¹⁶ The agenda has 92 paragraphs, but paragraph 59 gives outlines of 17 Sustainable Development Goals and associated 169 targets and 32 indicators.

The 17 goals that were adopted are listed and analysed in the table below for clarity and understanding.

Table 1: United Nations Sustainable Development 17 Goals

S/N	Goals	Goal’s Target
1.	No poverty	To end poverty in all forms everywhere. SDGs’ target is that by 2030, extreme poverty must come to an end globally.
2.	Zero Hunger	To end hunger; to achieve food security and improved nutrition and to promote sustainable agriculture.
3.	Good Health	Good health and well being for people. The goal target is to ensure healthy lives and to promote well-being target, to ensure healthy lives and to promote well-being for all at all ages.
4.	Quality Education	To ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and to promote long learning opportunities for all. Complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education.
5.	Gender Equality	To achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. The goal is to provide women and girls with equal access to education, health care, decent work, and politics and economic decision-making process.
6.	Clean Water and Sanitation	To ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all people of the world.
7.	Affordable and Clean Energy	To ensure access to affordable, reliable sustainable and modern energy for all.
8.	Decent Work and Economic Growth	To promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
9.	Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	To build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation.
10.	Reducing Inequalities	To reduce income inequality within and among countries. To eradicate extreme poverty, to sustain income growth for the bottom 40% of the population.
11.	Sustainable Cities and Communities	To make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. To ensure accessibility to safe and affordable housing.
12.	Responsible Consumption and Production	To ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
13.	Climate Action	Countries to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts by regulating emissions and promoting developments in renewable energy.
14.	Life Below Water	This is to conserve and sustain the use of oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

15.	Life on Land	To protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat deforestation, halt and reverse land degradation and biodiversity loss.
16.	Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	Promotion of peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development provision of access to justice for all and to build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels. This is to reduce violent, crimes, sex trafficking, forced labour and child abuse violence against and torture of children.
17.	Partnerships for the Goals.	Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development. Development of multi-stakeholder partnerships to share knowledge, expertise, technology and financial support is seen as critical to over success of the SDGs.

In summary, it is not an exaggeration to assert that the aims and objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals incidentally highlight the interlocked problems to development in developing nations. Therefore, against the need for developing nations to overcome the challenges of underdevelopment in the 21st century, both the leadership and followership must, as a matter of urgency, redouble efforts towards actualising the objectives of Sustainable Development Goals as outlined by the United Nations.¹⁶

OritaMefa Baptist Model Schools Contribution to UN SDGs

The three key areas where OBMS have contributed to the UN SDGs are on goals numbers 1, 4 and 5 (No Poverty, Gender Equality and Quality Education). These contributions are highlighted as follows:

Quality Education

The findings of this paper are that there is a rush in the recent for the desire and high rate at which parents are bent on getting their children admitted into OBMs in Ibadan based on the schools' excellent performances. The schools are quite equipped with well trained, qualified and professional teachers who are working assiduously towards the pupils' excellent performances. This paper has also found that some of their primary school pupils are given a double promotion from primary 4 to 6 and sometimes, 5 to the secondary schools due to their excellent results and class performances.

To continue providing quality education and a conducive spiritual and moral environment for their primary school graduates and pupils of other schools, Oritamefa Baptist Church through their former Pastor, Reverend Samuel Leigh started Oritamefa Baptist Model School, Total Garden branch in 1996. The school took off on 23rd September 1996 with 115 students, 9 teachers and 3 non-teaching staff. Meanwhile, "the primary purpose and objective of the school is to instil in any student passing through the school physical and academic discipline, humility and most importantly obedience to the word of God".¹⁷

Meanwhile, due to the overgrowing population of the School main campus at Total Garden and for ease of administration, and because of the increasing population of students and staff, the church on the 14th October 2012 carved out a junior section of the main school and resettled them in a separate area, which is today referred to as OBMs Annex Total Garden.

OBMS: Ring Road, Ibadan

In 2002, the Education Committee/schools' Board observed that many of the students who were coming to Total Garden were from Ring Road, Odo-Ona and Challenge areas of the city. This was the basis for the commencement of a new school in Ring Road to reduce the parent's burden of taking them down to Total Garden and to attract more students from these localities. The school commenced with an intake of 53 students on Monday 14th October 2002 with a new principal, teachers and an accountant to manage the school.

OBMS: Akobo Ibadan

Based on the rapid growth of the schools, overpopulation of the Total Garden branch of the school, and requests for more of OBMS presence that kept on coming to the school authority as a result of their pupils' excellent performances from several people, Akobo branch took off on Monday, 9th September 2019 with a population of 69 JSS 1 students with its new principal, 18 new teaching and 5 non-teaching members of staff. Since its inception, the population of the school has been growing tremendously.

OBMS Cambridge Advanced Level College, Total Garden, Ibadan

So as to strengthen Model School Secondary graduates for continued outstanding performance in the university and other higher institutions of learning, the church leadership established the OBMS Cambridge Advanced Level College on a temporary site on 25th July 2016. The aim for establishing the college is to prepare students for Cambridge as (Advanced Subsidiary) and A2 (Advanced Level) as well as JUPED (Joint University Preliminary Education Board) examinations for Direct Entry admission into Nigerian Universities and admission into foreign universities. Meanwhile, this college is also an Associate of Cambridge Assessment International Education, United Kingdom. The college also prepares students for IELTS, IGSCE, SAT, TOEFL examinations.

Moreover, the number of students enrolment and laurels won are analysed through the tables below.

Table 2: Estimated Student Enrollment

S/N	SCHOOL	J.S.S 1 – 3	S.S.S 1 – 3
1.	Total Garden, Ibadan	680	782
2.	Ring Road	360	391
3.	Akobo, Ibadan	404	202

Award and Laurels Won

Some of the prizes won amongst others are as follows:

1. In 2014, 6th best result in Nigeria for WASSCE.
 - 1st Best Result in WASSCE in South-West Nigeria.
2. In 2015, Best Result in Nigeria in NECO SSCE- David Oluwasayo Babalola.
 - 1st Best Candidate in WASSCE and NECO, Oyo state- David O. Babalola
 - 1st Overall Best Candidate in WAEC in Nigeria- David O. Babalola
 - 1st Joseph Ayo Babalola University Annual Quiz Competition.
3. In 2016- 1st Best School in Southwest Nigeria in WASSCE
4. In 2017,
 - November 2017- 2nd Hope Aid Essay Competition by Akinsola Shallom
 - December 2017 NSE Essay Competition in Nigeria- Opeyeoluwa Olanipekun
5. In 2018,
 - January 2018, 1st& 2nd Armstrong Essay Competition (UCH) Olanipekun Ope and Elendu Udochie.
 - May 2018- 2nd Bowen University, Iwo Chemistry Department Quiz Competition Okpala Terance/ Olanipekun Opeyeoluwa.
 - May 2018, - Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Faculty of Natural Science Quiz Competition- Apeji Paul, Olowookere Gold/ Osiyemi Pipeolu.
 - November 2018- 2nd WAEC Merit Award- Best candidate in Nigeria (Male)- Oluwatoni Adekunle (for 2017)
 - 1st WAEC Merit Award- Best Candidate in Nigeria (Female) Isabelle Irabor (for 2017).

Overall best WASSCE candidate in Nigeria- Isabelle Irabor (for 2017)

In recent times, some of the awards won (2019/2020) from a total of 23 awards, are listed below:

March 2019- 1st The Nigerian Society of Engineers Chairman's Science Quiz Award (IBDEC)- Akinola Oluwasegun and Olowookere Gold.

June 2019- 1st Overall Best Performance, 2019 ECWA Model College Annual Library and Debate- Priscilla Oluseyi, Olusola Fadare, Praise Adika and MoyinOluwa Adelowo.

July 2019- 50th Anniversary, Biology Quiz Competition- Zoological Department, U.I Olusola Fadare and Peter Olaniyi.

2019 Interschool Quiz Competition Physiotherapy Department, U.I.- Shamsudeen Sadiq, Olusola Fadare and Peter Olayiwola.

October 2019. 2nd Bowen University Quiz Competition (Chemistry Department)- Pipeolowa Osiyemi and Osionela Ogiogua.

December 2019- 2019 3rd NSE Essay Competition in Nigeria- Ayobami Adeoye

2nd NSE Essay Competition in Nigeria- Temiloluwa Oladipo

January 2020- 2nd Professor Adesanya and Professor Sanibare Intersecondary School Competition (Chemical Society of Nigeria) Esedebe Shikina

February 2020- 1st Winifred Awosika Foundation Annual Schools Challenge (WAFASC-Lagos) Moyinoluwa Adelowo and Praise Adika.

Summarily, between 2003-February 2020, the school has won a total number of 63 major awards. From the above achievements, one can prove that Oritamefa Baptist Model School is a force to reckon with among the secondary schools in Nigeria. This positively confirms the popular belief that generally, the Baptist Christians are the people of the book and that they are very learned and academically sound in providing the children with the necessary education for future academic pursuits in Nigeria and other parts of the world.

REMARKS: According to the principal address for 2019/2020 Academic of OBMs Ring Road, the students recorded 100% in all subjects; with all the students qualifying for National Universities admissions. In addition, the branch of the schools produced the current best male and female WASCE results and hence the overall best results in WASCE results in Nigeria thus the school is now the custodian of OMO N'OBA Erediuwa Awards for Best boy and best girl in Nigeria Secondary School examinations.

To support this fact, the tables listed below are evidences of OBMS student performances in their external examinations.

Table 3: OBMS Advanced Level College 2020 Session Outstanding Students

S/N	Names of Outstanding Students	Subject offered	Results obtained
1.	Laugher Coker	Physics, Maths, Chemistry	A*A*A
2.	Timilehin Ojo	Chemistry, Biology, Physics	A*A*A
3.	Oluwasegun Akinola	Physics, Chemistry, Biology	A*A*A
4.	Praise Oladosu	English Lit, Sociology, History	A, A, B
5.	Motunrayo Onadipe	History, Sociology, Eng. Lit	A, A, C
6.	Iyanuoluwa Wintola	Sociology, Eng. Lit, History	A, B, B
7.	Marvellous Adetunji	Physics, Maths, Chemistry	A, B, C
8.	Tunmininu Adelowo	Chemistry, Biology, Physics	B, B, C
9.	Ibukun Malomo	Physics, Math. Chem.	B, B, C

Table 4: Advance Level College Results for 2020/2021 Session

S/N	Names of Outstanding Students	Subject offered	Results
1.	Oluwdamilola Akinyele	Chemistry, Physics, Mathematics	A*A*A
2.	Adebowale Agbaje	Biology, Physics, Chemistry	A*A*A
3.	Grace Ovuakporie	Chemistry, Mathematics, Physics	A*A*A
4.	Hephzibah Olutona	History, Sociology, English-Literature	A, A, C
5.	Ayomide Ibikunle	Sociology, Economics, History	A, B, C
6.	Daniel Williams	Biology, Chemistry, Physics	A, C,C
7.	Esther Elijah	English-Lit, Sociology, History	B, B, C

Scholarship Award

It is one of the principles of Oritamefa Baptist Model Schools to award scholarships for the 3 students who have the best results on their WASCE for the pursue of their degrees in the universities of their choice. Likewise, for all graduating students of OBMS who considered OBMS Advanced College, the school's principle is to give a N50,000 deduction from their school fees. This is given as a way to appreciate their parents for investing in the lives of their children through OBMS.

OBMS Contributions to No Poverty

The contributions of OBMS to no poverty can be best illustrated through the below diagram.

Table 5: OBMS Staff Strength

S/N	Name of Schools	Academic Staff	Non-Academic Staff
1.	Total Garden	Around 100	Around 35
2.	Akobo Branch	35	8
3.	Ring Road Branch	70	20
4.	Advance College	12	5

From the above table, the records from these schools have displayed the contributions of OBMS to the elimination of poverty, zero hunger, and gender equality in Nigeria. The schools have no bad records of non-payment of staff salaries. Similarly, apart from the regular payment of staff monthly salaries, the schools are also known for their generousities to the staff in the forms of other incentives to motivate them to add more value to the school.

Gender Equality

OBMS are schools that have been good promoters of the gender equality of both staff and students. As of this 2020/2021 academic session, two out of the school principals are female. The schools also have a countable number of female staff. Likewise, all the students are given equal opportunities to excel in their academic pursuits. That is why many of their female students are high performers in their examinations and in representing the schools in the external competitions.

In a nutshell, OBMS have in no small measure have contributed to the attainment of gender equality in Nigeria. As of this year 2020, many of their school graduates are occupying many respectable positions in Nigeria, and many who are outside Nigeria have been found to be doing well.

In other to assess the performance of the school in an objective way, as well as enable the school authorities, this research work carried out interviews with some of the parents of the students in the premises of the school. The interview was conducted on the campus of the Total Garden school with some of the volunteer parents.

Table 6: Parents perspective on OBMS

S/N	Names of Parents	Remarks & Recommendations
1.	Dr Felix O. Ibikunle	OBMS is a school that is known for diligence and discipline. The school has a track record of high academic standards traceable to the commitment of the teachers across the board. The school is a model and modest that would not compromise its reputation and integrity. Finally, OBMS is a beacon of good hope for parents and students at the end of their children sojourn in OBMS. The standard should not be compromised. The school should provide an avenue for the students to participate in sports for the overall wellness of the total dull child because all work and no play makes Jack a dull boy. School's PTA should be resuscitated.
2.	Mrs Tayo Alimi	The students are doing their bit in performances. Teachers need more encouragement from the school's management to enable them to do more. The management should do the needful to reduce the mass exodus of teachers to other competitors. The school should do more. Let the teachers be encouraged to do their work without fear. There should be a sense of belonging, to enable teachers to work joyfully without fear. This will lead to better performances by the students. PTA should be reintroduced.
3.	Mrs B.F. Awotedu	The school is very good academically. I brought my children to this school because of competition. There is a need to prepare students for more competitions. I, therefore, recommend that PTA meetings should be resuscitated to allow interactions between the school and parents. There must also be an improvement in the form of class notes by the students and enough time to be given to the students to write their notes.
4.	Mrs Adigun F.O.	The best school I have seen so far. But the school should bring back to life the PTA meeting. It is also advisable to assist parents by a fairly downward adjustment of students school fees.
5.	Mrs O.L. Agboola	The school charges for student food should be looked into as the food being given is not in line with the amount. The standard should be upgraded. Meanwhile, the school is of a high standard, and the school curriculum is perfect.
6.	Mrs Omowumi Muyiwa	The standard is very good and acceptable. I brought my children to this school because of the standard. My advice is to rejuvenate the PTA to enable parents to have a say in the running of the school and to add value to the standard of the school.

7.	Mr Adetunji I.B.	As an administrator, my perspective is that the school and the teachers are excellently doing well. My observation is that the tuition fee is on a high sight. In other schools in Ibadan, discounts are given to parents with more than one student in their schools. There should be an avenue for parents and teachers interactions to enable parents to express their minds, this will help the school in no small measure. Meanwhile, the school hygiene is very good and commendable. The standard of the food needs to be upgraded because as of now it does not correspond with the amount being paid to the school for food, especially, beans are always badly prepared for it lacks oil and is too watery. There should also be balanced diets. Sports activities should be improved upon this is because the school policies have negated sporting activities. The school is also known for academics without allowing social activities such as Man O War, Red Cross and others. There is also an overflowing of students in the classes. Academic at OBMS is 90%, whereas sports in other schools around the globe takes at least 30% of their activities. Moreover, we plead that the school authority should reconsider returning the woman who sells Jolof rice at the parking space back to her place to enable parents who wish to wait for their wards to entertain themselves.
8.	Mrs Bukola Oladejo	My advice for the school should set a committee to supervise the meal they are serving the wards. They should pray before admitting the new set of children to the school (“won ti keran mero”).
9.	Mrs A.M. Aboyade	Oritamefa Baptist Model Schools are one of the best schools in Nigeria. They are known for a very high standard of discipline. In most external exams, their students always come out as the best. They have good infrastructural facilities like laboratories and libraries. They have well trained and experienced teachers to help students bring out the best in themselves.
10.	Mama Grace Omonaiye	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There should be more effective communication between the parents and the management. 2. Teachers are supposed to be role models and mentors to the students, many of the teachers are not friendly, students fear them too much. 3. Notes given to the students should be such that, they can complete within school time. Most students use their closing time to copy notes. 4. Sporting activities should be encouraged, no inter sport for some years now, not good at all.

III. Recommendations

Oritamefa Baptist Model Schools, Ibadan, is without a doubt one of the high performers in Nigeria with integrity and high discipline. For OBMS to remain as one of the best schools in Nigeria and to enable them to keep on being relevant in the contributions to the attainment of quality education in Nigeria, this paper hereby recommends as follows:

First, there is a need to accede to the popular request from the parents to resuscitate the parents-teachers association that was cancelled some years ago. This will enable parents and guardians to have an avenue to make suggestions and to present their grievances to the school management.

Second, the school managements should extend their hands of generosity through scholarship awards to children of low estate irrespective of their academic ranking. This is because this school original motive was not for excessive profit-making, but the expansion of God's kingdom on earth, and to raising future leaders who have moral upbringings, integrity and godliness

Third, the present school fees should be downwardly reviewed to enable many others to send their children to this school to enjoy qualitative education. Furthermore, this paper is of opinion that Oritamefa Baptist Church should consider extending the tentacles of this school to other parts of Oyo state in particular and other regions of Nigeria, in general, to enable more students to enjoy this quality education.

In addition, more incentives and encouragements should be given to the teachers to enable them to give more to the students and this will eventually lead to excellent performances and winning of more laurels for the schools. Likewise, if the teachers are well-taken care of, there will be a reduction in the mass exodus of the teachers. Furthermore, this paper hereby recommends a higher review of the teacher's retirement age from its present 55 years to 65 years before retirement to enjoy their loyalty, professionalism and experiences. Finally, it is advisable for the school to give a higher priority to sporting activities of their students so as to bring out the best out of their sporting talents which can lead provide a platform for them to earn a living and make the country proud.

IV. Conclusion

This paper's opinion about OBMS is that the schools have enjoyed tremendous growth in recent years and have been schools that have outstanding records that may be difficult to beat by many of their competitors in Oyo state in particular and in Nigeria in general. Furthermore, the church has been blessed with good spiritual leaders who have foresight. Likewise, the church has just been blessed with the new Senior Pastor the person of Revd Dr Diran Adeleke who is dynamic, young and agile.

This paper, therefore, concludes that for the school to keep on being relevant in the educational sector in Nigeria, the school management should ensure that they do not jeopardise the academic principles of the schools. The academic standard of the school should not in any way be compromised nor played with. The newly called Senior Pastor of the church, Revd Dr Diran Adeleke should use his agility, wide experience and academic achievements to improve on the quality of the schools to enable OBMS to keep on retaining the standard that has been set for many years, and to continue to be schools that are on the top of the performing chart in Nigeria's academic records.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Benedict, D.A. General History of the Baptist Denomination in America and other parts of the world. Lewis Colby. Retrieved on November 13, 2019.
- [2.] Encyclopedia Britannica: "Baptist". Retrieved online from <https://www.britannica.com> on 13th November 2019.
- [3.] History of Oritamefa Baptist Church, Ibadan: The church at the Cross Roads 1959-2008, Ibadan, Baptist Press. P. 1
- [4.] Ibid
- [5.] Ibid
- [6.] Ibid
- [7.] Ibid
- [8.] Amodu, Akeem, 2019. Philosophy of Science and Sustainability. A concise introduction. Jericho Ibadan, College Press.
- [9.] Dpicampaigns. About the Sustainable Development Goals: United Nations Sustainable Development. Retrieved November 9, 2019.
- [10.] "Global Goals/Policy and Advocacy". Sight savers 25th September, 2017. Retrieved 11th February, 2020.

- [11.] Wikipedia: Sustainable Development Goals. Retrieved from <https://www.wikipedia.org> on February 20, 2020.
- [12.] The history of Sustainable Development in the United Nations. Rio 20 UN Conference Sustainable Development 20-22 June, 2012.
- [13.] Development, World Commission on Environment and our Common Future, chapter 2: Towards Sustainable Development – A/42/427, Annex Chapter 2-UN Documents: Gathering a body of global agreements, www.undocuments.net
- [14.] New Open Working Group to Propose Sustainable Development Goals for Action by General Assembly's 68th Session, Meetings coverage and press releases" un.org.
- [15.] United Nations Official Documents. un.org. Retrieved 20th February, 2020.
- [16.] Amodu ibid.